

The Motivations of Ethiopian Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract:- Teacher motivation plays a key role in promoting excellence in teaching and learning and is also essential to the teaching and learning process. However, few teachers in Ethiopia are likely to be unmotivated. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to investigate the factors that influence the work motivation of teachers in public secondary schools in Chelia District, West Shoa Zone, Oromia Regional Government State. A cross-sectional survey design was used for this study. The sample respondents were selected from the sampling frame using simple random sampling. Using Kothari's questionnaire formula, 80 selected teachers from three public secondary schools in the Chelia district were identified and 5 key informant interviews and 3 focus groups were conducted. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics such as binary logistic regression were used for quantitative data analysis, and narrative analysis was performed for qualitative data to meet the stated objectives. The descriptive analysis found that 73.75 percent of the teachers were demotivated while 26.25 percent of them were motivated. The analysis of the binary logit model showed that school leadership positively and significantly influenced the motivational state of teachers.

Keywords:- Teachers, Public Secondary School, Motivational State of Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Organizational fulfilment is about encouraging employees to perform at their best possible stage and exert extraordinary effort. Employee motivation, overall organizational performance, and earnings are interconnected and cannot be separated. Global and Dai and Sternberg (2004) suggest that excessive levels of activity dissatisfaction, stress, and burnout can negatively affect motivation and overall activity performance. Research on the elements influencing the motivation of trainers is necessary to obtain educational dreams in any learning institution. Shah, M. et al. (2012) discussed elements that can influence the overall performance and motivation of lecturers.

These include inadequate income and non-earning benefits, the painting itself, the character of the painting environment, the private wooing of undergraduates and supervisors, disciplinary problems of undergraduates, parents, networking and instructor coaching beliefs, and administrative difficulties. In addition, instructors' motivation is influenced by various elements such as rewards or incentives, intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, pride in the activity, private improvement, social fame, and popularity.

An effective trainer improvement arrangement must have a full degree of these elements to promote core competencies and attitudes among capability instructors.

The unique weight of information itself must be distributed in favour of multi-activity programs that have a direct impact on the actual classroom situation (Anderson, J. et al, 2002).

Many studies have been conducted around the world to address these challenging situations. However, these problems defied the world and hardened. Instructors appear to enter coaching for intrinsic rather than extrinsic reasons (Dinham & Scott, 1998, observations conducted in developed international locations including the United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), Australia, and New Zealand).

These elements include pupil achievement, college student support, fantastic relationships with college students and others, self-service boom, etc., growing warm private relationships with children, elevated coaching projects, excessive coaching autonomy, solid management, and administrative support (Shann, 1998).). In growing international locations, instructors are influenced to go into coaching with the help of extrinsic motives instead of intrinsic ones, ie salary, absence of scholars, and lack of instructor involvement in internal decision-making (Bennell, 2004). Bennel (2004) observes that instructor salaries and blessings of various substances were too low to meet the wishes of individuals and families to survive in many African international locations.

According to Bush & Montecinos, C, (2019), this research found that in many African international locations, faculties operate with terrible buildings, very little equipment, untrained instructors, loss of basic centers that include water, electricity and sanitation, and newcomers who have regular hunger.

In Ethiopia, the educational resource is being questioned due to the rapid increase in the number of pupils. Research Center for British Teachers, (2008) identified many factors that contribute to poor overall training performance, such as low admiration for instructors, insufficient pay, and vulnerable training reform, dire trends in instructors' living conditions, and failure control and management of the school.

Ethiopian authorities have expressed their commitment to developing the best training at many academic meetings and events, and the purpose of continuous professional development (CPD) has changed to increase instructors' overall performance in the classroom and improve student outcomes.

All instructors should be actively involved in gaining knowledge about the method, running with their colleagues, identifying their own desires, and participating in different sports. The MoE also brought in software called the Training Best Development Package (GEQIP) to improve the best of training.

The Department for Training has prioritized continuous professional development (CPD) in the belief that the right instructors are of enormous value to national improvement. However, the Ethiopian training apparatus has failed to select and cope with the elements that cause the instructors to be dissatisfied with the activity. In Ethiopia, several researchers, among them Gobena, G. A. (2018), found that elements such as dissatisfaction portraying a group of workers, instructors having no freedom, disrespecting undergraduates and misbehaving, and lack of job autonomy can affect instructors' motivation.

In Chelia District, there are a number of challenging situations regarding the contribution of the sports instructor in the secondary faculty, for example, 65% of them are reluctant to participate in college sports, surprise absences, late arrivals, stimulating coaching, and loss of interest in counseling and qualified instructors. This observation fills the space that the researcher encounters from the above research.

➤ *Research Questions*

The view was transformed into a view guided by the following study questions:

- What has changed in the instructors' idea towards the popularity of instructor motivation in public secondary faculties with a look inside the area?
- What influence did institutional elements have on the motivation of teachers at public secondary faculties in the given area?

- What influence did demographic elements have on the motivation of teachers at public secondary faculties?
- What influence did interpersonal family members have on the motivation of teachers in public secondary faculties in this area?

➤ *General Objective*

The standard aim of this view has changed into tracking the elements that influence the popularity of teachers' motivation to paint in public secondary faculties in the Chelsea district.

• *Specific Goals*

- ✓ To explore the concepts of instructors towards the popularity of instructor motivation in public secondary faculties with an inside look at the field.
- ✓ Investigate the influence of institutional elements on the motivation of teachers at public secondary faculties with an inside view of the field.
- ✓ Perceive the function of demographic elements on the motivation of teachers at public secondary faculties from the point of view of the area.
- ✓ To evaluate the influence of interpersonal family members on the motivation of teachers at public secondary faculties with an inside view of the field.

➤ *Maslow's theory of the Hierarchy of Needs*

Abraham Maslow emphasizes the concept of human desires which is primarily based entirely on a hierarchical version starting from the lower-order desires from the lowest to the higher-order desires at the top (Zalenski, R. J. et al., 2006). He diagnosed that human desires are organized in a chain of levels, a hierarchy of importance. According to this hierarchy, Maslow diagnosed 5 human desires.

➤ *A Conceptual Framework of Factors Affecting the Motivation of Secondary School Teachers in Chelia District*

The researcher develops the conceptual framework for this research by reviewing previous work that shows the relationships between the independent and dependent variables.

Since this study focuses on the factors affecting the motivation of secondary school teachers: the dependent variable is the motivational state of the teacher, which in turn affects the performance of students, while the independent variables are job satisfaction, administrative problems, inadequate salary, and other benefits, disciplinary problems of students, training and development, work environment and interpersonal factor

Fig 1 A Conceptual Framework

II. STUDY METHODOLOGY

➤ Research Design

Research organization refers to a general approach chosen to combine the characteristic components of a view in a coherent and logical manner. Explanatory studies turned into a sort of layout of studies about this view. Studies described during the explanatory time period became quantitative in nature and measured relationships between variables.

The collected statistics were converted to analysis using descriptive statistical techniques. In this view, every method of qualitative and quantitative studies became used.

A cross-sectional survey was modified to hire to answer this study question.

A cross-sectional view of the distribution, statistical series, and single-factor rounding over time, because cross-sectional designs commonly use survey techniques to collect statistical data, are extremely inexpensive, and last 3.1.1. Target population

A population or observable universe is any institution of people or facilities that has one or more features in an unusual location that are of interest to the researcher (Cooper 1996). All three public secondary schools in Chelia District in WSZ (West Shewa Zone) become the target population for screening. Look at the concentrated 167 instructors in secondary schools in the Chelia district (Chelia Educational Office, 2020).

• Sampling Technique and Sample Size

3 public secondary faculties within the district were studied. A purposive sampling method is used to select the districts, just as a simple random sampling method is used to select the trainer respondents. An important advantage of the simple random sampling method is that it provided an equal opportunity for presenters to be sampled for viewing.

There are 3 secondary faculties with inside the district, all protected inside the actual view. A total of eighty respondents can be targeted, representing 90% of the entire population of high school coaches within the district.

It consisted of seventy-three instructors, 6 directors, and 1 supervisor. Gay (2003) advises that 10% of smart people are good enough to function by pattern. The researcher subsequently considers 95% to be a sufficient consultant for this view. Where n is the length of the consultant sample, N is the entire faculty of the secondary faculty, which is determined as the entire 167 within the 3 faculties (Chelia Academic Office, 2020), and e is the error rate. The pattern length is determined using the formulation given using Kothari (2004)

Where n = desired sample size

N = population size (167)

$P=0.5$ $q=0.5$

Z = 95% confidence interval which is 1.96

A total of 80 teachers were a simple random sampling technique from each of the 3 schools used in the actual study.

➤ Data Collection Methods

Data collection methods used in this study includes individual survey questionnaires, focus group discussions, key informant interviews, and field observation (non-participant observation).

➤ Data Analysis and Interpretation

The statistics turned into an accumulated, summarized, coded, and analysed method through the use of SPSS model 25 converted to provide by means using tables. Tabulation was concerned that the summarization method was changed to accumulated statistics in a table to facilitate calculations of various variables during statistical evaluation.

In this study, a descriptive approach to the statistical evaluation was used, which will describe the modern situation of schools. Therefore, descriptive statistical means such as frequency and percentage, regressions were changed to use. In addition, the chi-rectangles look at the hired and check the result.

• Econometric Analysis

A multivariate analysis was performed to determine the factors that are associated with the teacher's motivational state).

A binary logistic regression model was used to test the hypothesized explanatory factors on the dependent variables.

✓ Model Specifications

The binary logistic regression version was changed to adjust because the dependent variable (trainer motivation status) is a dichotomous variable: where represents while academics are uninspired and while the trainer is inspired.

According to Gujarati (2004), the logistic version can be written in the phrases odds ratio and log odd ratio, which makes it possible to understand the translation of the coefficients. In this study, the odds ratio is the ratio of the chance that the coach could be de-inspired (P_i) to the chance that he could be inspired ($1-P_i$). Before running a version of the binary logistic regression, unbiased variables could be checked for the lifestyle of the multi-company linearity problem.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE STUDY

This chapter focused exclusively on the results obtained from the quantitative evaluation of the information achieved using SPSS version 25 and the narrative analysis/generalization of the ideas, notes, and comments extracted at a certain point in the work area. Results were displayed in the following order: Frequency and percentage, univariate evaluation, bivariate evaluation, and multivariate evaluation (binary logistic regression).

➤ Background Characteristics of Respondents

Throughout the data collection using the survey method and rule, pre-defined vital variables for tracking the determinants of motivation of reputation instructors were captured and conducted for interpretation and analysis.

Demographic and institutional variables of these respondents during the survey with the internal investigated environment, namely: Salary, fringe benefit, Administrative support, Job satisfaction, Training and development, praise of gadgets, school control and management, image burden, Gender, Age, level of education, Workspace layout, painting environment, instructor-pupil, instructor-colleague, instructor-supervisor/supervisor, instructor-mother and father relationships were mentioned in the elements inside the following tables and figures.

➤ Descriptive Analysis (Univariate)

• Gender of Respondents

Gender became one of the variables that were used to interpret and examine the demographic characteristics of the respondents in this study. Survey results from determining three well-known shows that 81.3 percent of sample respondents were male at the same time as relaxation 18.8 percent were female

Fig 2 Percentage of Respondents via way of means of Intercourse Distribution

Source: Computed from Survey Data (2021)

• Age of Respondents

One of the continuous variables that were part of the survey questionnaire over the length of the survey was changed to the age of the respondent. As shown in Table 4, the common age of the respondents was forty years (46) and the standard deviation changed to 7.45412.

The minimum age of the respondents was 27 and 57 years, respectively. This indicates that more than 1/2 of the respondents' normal age changed to forty over the course of the survey.

Table 1 Age of Respondents

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age	80	40.5750	7.45412	27	57
Source: Computed from Survey Data (2021)					

• Educational Status of Respondents

The distribution of respondents according to their educational attainment is shown below in Figure 4. A larger proportion of the total number of respondents (67.5%) had a bachelor's degree, while 32.5 percent had a master's degree.

Fig 3 Percentage Distribution Of Respondents By Education
Source: Calculated from survey data (2021)

• Year of the Service Status of the Respondents

During the data collection process, sample respondents were asked for their approximate years of provider fame. The responses received from the respondents were defined as given under the 5th determination which shows that 72.5 percent, 16.25 percent, (10%), and 1.25 percent of the respondents were below 26 years, 26-29 years, 30-35 years or 36 years of glory of the provider.

The final result suggests that the majority of respondents who made offers to their college students were young enough to offer a good enough education and provider in the event that they were challenged through means of school review.

Fig 4 Year of the Service Status of the Respondents

During the data collection process, respondents were asked about their motivation as teachers. The responses obtained from the respondents were explained as shown in the figure below which shows that 73.75 percent of the teachers were demotivated while the remaining 26.25 percent of the teachers were motivated.

- *Teachers' perceptions of the motivational status of teachers in public secondary schools in the study area*
- *The influence of institutional factors on the motivation of teachers in public secondary schools in the given area*

How happy or disillusioned are academics in secondary faculties with earnings and various benefit factors (earnings, fringe benefits, and praise system), control factors (administrative support, control and management of the college, workload, job satisfaction, education, and development)?

- *Factor 1: Salary and other benefits from academics' perspective on their salaries*

The frequency and odds of academics' responses indicate whether they were satisfied or disillusioned with their salaries (see Table 5 below).

Fig 5 Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Teacher Motivation Status

Table 2 Teachers' Views on Their Salaries

Statement	Disagree%	Agree f (%)
My salary compares well with my qualification(s)	42(52.5)	19(23.8)
My salary is appropriate for my Experience	42(52.5)	12(15)
My salary improves my commitment	40(50)	11(13.8)
My salary covers all my basic needs	45(56.3)	12(15)
My salary keeps me in my job	40(50)	11(13.8)

Source: Calculated from survey data (2021)

The results in Table 2 above showed that trainer respondents primarily disagreed with all five statements. Thus, the facts tended to reflect a pattern of dissatisfaction among coaches in terms of income.

The maximum place of dissatisfaction or confrontation needed for the cause regardless of whether the achieved monthly income of the academicians covered all their primary needs (n=45, 56.3%) along with the adequacy of their salaries to their experience (n=42, 52.5%)) and whether their income is compared to their education (n=42, 52.5%) or not.

The place of dissatisfaction was linked to whether their income was more desirable, the popularity they had in the community, the ranking between the instructors' salaries and the pursuit of work, and whether the monthly income or not acquired academics imposed their work (n=40, 50%) and

n=40, 50% of respondents expressed their confrontation with the statement "My income improves my commitment.

In addition, the final survey result of the key informant interviews and FGDs indicated that the coaching career is interesting.

However, this noble career is undermined by the low salaries of academics. The authorities need to review and increase the salaries of instructors to be equal to the salaries of various government employees, considering that we instructors have the right to adjust to the internal resources of our United States of America and are essential to the growth of instructor salaries in line with the current rate of inflation.

As compared to various civil servants, the salaries of instructors are below average. So the authorities must not forget our contribution and adjust our salaries accordingly.

In addition to the above, academics wanted non-income incentives. These incentives should consist of housing development land or housing allowances and transport, fitness, and education allowances.

➤ *Instructors' Views on their Fringe Benefits*

The frequencies and probabilities of academics' responses indicate whether or not they were satisfied or disappointed with their Fringe benefits (Table 3), their fringes, and opportunities for development and promotion.

Table 3 Teachers' Views on their Marginal Benefit

Statement	Disagree f (%)	Agree f (%)
I am pleased with the vacation leave I get.	41(51.4)	12(15)
I am happy with the allowances given	41(51.4)	9(11.3)
The quality of in-service training is good	39(48.8)	14(17.5)

Table 6 above shows the frequency, percentages, and manner of responses of all presenters to the 4 statements that focused on fringe benefits. Similarly, the majority of trainer respondents (N=41, 51.3%) are no longer satisfied with the types of allowances they have been allocated. About three-quarters of respondents expressed their dissatisfaction with the enjoyable education within the provider they received, even though simply more than 1/2 of the lecturers disagreed that they were satisfied with the excursion vacation (N=41, 51.4%).

- *Factor 2: Management System*

- *Teachers' Views on Administrative Guides*

The frequency and options of the teachers' answers indicated their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the leadership. This protected the executive handbook they showed (Table 4).

Table 4 Teachers' Opinions on their Administrative Support

Statement	Agree f (%)	Dis agree f (%)
I am satisfied with the administrative support I receive at school	13(16.3)	44(55)
Administrative support enhances my commitment	15(18.8)	38(47.5)
There is sufficient instructional material support	9(11.3)	44(55)
My school has good security	12(15)	44(55)
I get enough support with student disciplinary problems	18(22.5)	43(53.8)
The school administrative support good teacher-student relationships	14(17.5)	36(45)
The school administration evaluates my work fairly	15(18.8)	44(55)

Table four above provides academics' views on the seven statements making up the executive support variable.

This table shows that the maximum number of respondents was disappointed by each of the seven statements. Thus, the instructors were disappointed with the practices of the faculty management. More than two-thirds of academics expressed dissatisfaction with the delivery of teaching materials (N=44, 55%). In addition, nearly two-thirds of supervisor respondents said they had a poor view of help provided with admiration for student discipline problems (n=43, 53.8%), faculty leadership (N=44, 55%), and impact on faculty. management has a level of commitment to academics (N=36, 45%).

More than 1/2 of those surveyed expressed their dissatisfaction with faculty security (N=44, 55%) and the fairness of faculty management's evaluation gadget for academic image evaluation (N=44, 55%).

- *Instructors' Views on their Workload*

The frequency, percentages, and attitude of the academics in the responses indicated their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the leadership. This overlapped the number of paintings they showed (Table 5).

Table 5 Teachers' Views On their Workload

Statement	Disagree f (%)	Agree f (%)
I am satisfied with my workload	40(50)	21(26.3)
I am happy with my working hours	39(48.8)	16(20)
The demands of my job are fair	39(48.8)	13(16.7.3)
I have enough time to participate in social activities	37(46.3)	13(16.3)

Source: Computed from Survey Data (2021)

Table 5 shows that more than 48% of the respondents were disappointed with the amount of time they would take to participate in social activities (N=37, 46.3%).

Only another 1/2 of respondents were disappointed with the workload of their schools and the operating hours (48.8% and 40%, respectively). The object of this organization that was met with negativity was that the needs in their activities were fair - 39 (48.8%) disagreed.

➤ *Teachers' Views on the Reward System in Their School*

The frequency, percentages, and manner of teachers' responses indicated their pride or dissatisfaction with the leadership. This protected the praise device they showed (Table 6).

Table 6 Teachers' Views on their Reward System

Statement	Disagree f(%)	Agree f(%)
The pay given to teachers is worth the services they render	45(56.3)	14(17.5)
Hardworking teachers are encouraged by giving them presents	42(52.5)	11(13.8)
Teachers are promoted on the basis of their qualifications and motivation	46(57.5)	8(10)
Teachers output outweigh the pay they receive in terms of salary	37(46.3)	12(15)
Teachers who get low pay with regard to their inputs normally get de-motivated affecting motivation	46 (57.5)	13(16.3)

The findings in Table 6 indicate that 45 (56.3%) of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the salary provided to instructors is really worth the offer they provide. Look further found that 32 (35%) of those surveyed strongly disagreed that hard-working instructors are advocated through the use of gifting.

We found that 13 (16.3%) respondents strongly agreed with the statement that instructors are promoted in their qualifications and overall performance in this idea. From the findings you look at, it can be said that instructors' praise structures influence their motivation. In support of these findings, Andrew (2004) found that staff commitment is primarily based solely on rewards and recognition. From the findings we have reviewed, it can be concluded that praise structures have an effect on instructor motivation. Respondents were asked to list other factors affecting instructor motivation among instructors.

They pointed out that the individuals who coach academically terrible college students are not rewarded in any way and that the rewards are primarily based solely on the overall performance of the college students in national exams and as a result those whose college students no longer skip their exams are not rewarded. , therefore they may be much less motivated.

• *Relationship Factors*

Interpersonal relationships can also influence teachers' motivation.

Table 7 Illustrates Teachers' Views on their Relationships with Students

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	54	67.5
	No	26	32.5
	Total	80	100

Source: Calculated from survey data (2021)

The well-known Table 7 shows that academics were generally annoyed by their courting of students - this happened with 54 (67.5) more respondents who are now no longer satisfied with the behavior and subject of students.

However, approximately three out of 26 (32.5) of the sample were satisfied with the relationships they had with their students, the comments students gave them, and the way they treated the student.

Key informants additionally answered that student behaviour and subject matter difficulties could influence the trainer's motivation to wait for their magnificence with the complete hobby. Most instructors have no fondness for waiting for the magnificence with which the pupil troubles the subject; even this issue was almost solved in the secondary faculties of Chelia Woreda, and the principals tried many times to clarify, but the difficulties resisted and increased in the unique redundant faculties.

➤ *Teachers' Views on teacher-teacher Relationships*

In addition, interpersonal relationships with their colleagues can influence teachers' motivation. Table eight illustrates teachers' perspectives on their relationships with students.

Table 8 Teachers' Views on Teacher-Teacher Relationships

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	55	68.8
	No	24	30.0
	Total	79	98.8

Source: Calculated from Survey Data (2023)

Table 8 presents the frequency, percentages, satisfaction, or dissatisfaction scores of the academic staff's view of teacher-colleagues. This indicates that Ethiopian instructors in the secondary faculties of Chelia Woreda are sociable and value their relationships with their colleagues. Instructors expressed a strong great feeling about the 55(68.8) elements that proved us most academics mentioned pleasure with the honour they received from their colleagues with the relationships between many workers of individuals and with the behaviour of their colleagues.

• *Teachers' Perspective on Teacher-Differentiation Relationships*

In addition, interpersonal relationships with their principals can influence teachers' motivation. Table 10

illustrates teachers' perspectives on their relationships with students.

Table 9 Teachers' Views on Teacher-Differentiation Relationships

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	53	66.3
	No	27	33.8
Total		80	100.0

Table 10 indicates that, in general, the tutors were very disillusioned with the relationship between the trainer and the figure, as indicated by the table of 53 (66.3) respondents, which was justified by the fact that there may not be any daily and sincere relationships between the trainer and the students” the mother and father of their schools.

• *Analysis of Two Varieties*

There have been various methods of assessing the association between two variables. The Pearson-Chi-square test was one way to examine a bivariate relationship. Chi-square was used to measure the degree of association

Table 10 Chi-Square Test Result of the Association between Teacher’s Motivation Status and Demographic Variables

Variables	Teacher’s Motivation Status				Total Frequency	T ² test	Df	P-Value
	Motivated		De-Motivated					
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent				
Sex								
Male	16	24.6	49	75.4	65	100		
Female	5	33.3	10	66.7	15	100	0.478	1 0.489
Years of Services								
Below 26 years	16	27.6	42	72.4	58	100		
26-29 years old	2	15.4	11	84.6	13	100	1.725	3 0.631
30-35 years old	3	37.5	5	62.5	8	100		
36 years and Above	0	0	1	100	1	100		

Source: Survey Result (2021)

Regarding the relationship between years of teaching service and teacher motivation status, the proportion of demotivated teachers was higher among teachers aged 26–29 years (84.6%) than among teachers who had years of service. under 26 (72.4%) and between 30-35 years old (62.5%). The results of the cross-tabulation ($t_2 = 1.725, P > 0.1, df = 3$) revealed that the association between years of teaching service and teachers' motivational status was insignificant (see Table 11 above).

➤ *The Influence of Interpersonal Relationships on the Motivation of Teachers in Public Secondary Schools well-Fitting:*

• *Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients*

The Omnibus test statistic was used to examine whether there was a linear relationship between the probability of teacher motivation status (criterion) and the predictor variables. An omnibus test P-value statistic of less than 0.05 indicated that binary logistic regression could be used to model the data. The results in Table 18 below

between given independent variables and dependent variables while holding the effect of other variables constant.

The relationship between teacher motivational status and demographic variables

• *Sex*

Gender was one of the demographic variables that were related to teacher motivation status. The relationship between gender and teacher motivational status as shown in Table 11 below shows that among the 65 male teachers included in the sample, 75.4 percent of the teachers were demotivated, while 66.7 percent of the female teachers out of the total of 15 female teachers included in the sample were demotivated motivated. This confirms that male teachers were significantly demotivated compared to female teachers in the researched area. Pearson's Chi-Square results show that there was no statistically significant relationship between gender and the teacher's motivational state ($\chi^2 = 0.478, P > 0.1, df = 1$).

showed that the chi-square model and significance levels for the null hypothesis test that all p-values are equal to zero ($P < 0.001$)

Table 11 Omnibus Tests Of Model Coefficients

	Chi-square	Df	Sig.
Step	40.136	21	.007
Block	40.136	21	.007
Model	40.136	21	.007

Source: Model Result (2021)

• *Model Summary*

Although there is no direct analogous (similar) statistic in logistic regression with the coefficient of determination (R-squared), the model summary in Table 18 provides some approximation. In this case, the Cox & Snell R square was 0.394, indicating that about 39.4 percent of the variation in teacher motivation status (the outcome variable) was explained by the independent variable, while the Nagelkerke R square was 0.577, which meant that about 57.7 percent

variation on teacher motivation status (dependent variable) was explained by regressor variables.

Table 12 Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	51.969 ^a	.394	.577

Table 13 Results of Binary Logistic Regression Model

Step	Variables	Variables in the Equation					Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
		B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.		Lower	Upper
	Sex (1)	-1.520	1.326	1.314	1	.252	.219	.016	2.940
	Age	-.025	.079	.105	1	.746	.975	.836	1.137
	Educational Level (1)	.353	1.196	.087	1	.768	1.423	.137	14.827
	current salary(1)	-3.537	1.904	3.449	1	.063	.029	.001	1.216
	current encouragement fringe benefit (1)	-1.753	1.463	1.435	1	.231	.173	.010	3.050
	Administrative support (1)	-.534	.978	.299	1	.585	.586	.086	3.982
	Work load (1)	.242	1.075	.051	1	.822	1.274	.155	10.479
	Job satisfaction(1)	-1.442	1.215	1.409	1	.235	.236	.022	2.558
	School Leadership (1)	3.233	1.220	7.023	1	.008	25.35	2.321	276.984
	Teachers Management system(1)	-1.135	1.251	.823	1	.364	.322	.028	3.732
	Teachers Management system(2)	-.884	1.789	.244	1	.621	.413	.012	13.764
	Teachers Management system (3)	3.148	2.390	1.735	1	.188	23.294	.215	2520.65
	Teachers Management system (4)	-5.915	2.962	3.988	1	.046	.003	.000	.896
	Work environment /conditions			6.256	4	.181			
	Work environment (1)	-3.350	1.865	3.228	1	.072	.035	.001	1.356
	Work environment (2)	-.167	1.990	.007	1	.933	.846	.017	41.831
	Work environment(3)	-3.863	2.279	2.872	1	.090	.021	.000	1.830
	Work environment (4)	-2.434	3.230	.568	1	.451	.088	.000	49.251
	Sufficient instructional material available			4.350	4	.361			
	Sufficient instructional material (1)	1.395	1.258	1.229	1	.268	4.036	.343	47.545
	Sufficient instructional material(2)	-1.214	1.791	.460	1	.498	.297	.009	9.925
	Sufficient instructional material(3)	-.404	2.065	.038	1	.845	.668	.012	38.230
	Sufficient instructional material (4)	-27.78	19704	.000	1	.999	.000	.000	.
	Constant	9.942	5.942	2.799	1	.094	20784		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Sex , Age , Educational Level, Current salary , Current encouragement fringe benefit giving, administrative support , Work load , Job satisfaction, school leadership , Teachers Management system , Work environment /conditions, Sufficient instructional material available.

Source: Model Result (2021)

Note: Statistically significant at: * P<10 %(0.1) ** P < 5% (0.05); *** P < 1 %(0.01) = Regression coefficient, S.E.= Standard Error , Sig = Significance (P-Value), EXP (B) = odd ratio, RC = Reference Category, Df = Degree

➤ Discussion on the Topic Significant and Non-Significant Predictor Variable

The result of the binary logit model shows that out of the assumed twelve independent variables, four variables significantly influenced the teacher's motivational state. Thus, school management positively and significantly affects the state of teachers' motivation, while the current salary, teacher management system, and work environment affect the state of teachers' motivation negatively and significantly. However, eight variables (gender, age, and level of education, current marginal benefit of support, administrative support, workload, job satisfaction, and sufficient available learning materials) were found to be statistically insignificant.

• Current Salary

The result of the binary logistic regression model in Table 23 shows that the current salary was one of the variables that affect the teacher's motivational state. It shows that the odd ratio of demotivated teachers increases by 0.029 if individual teachers were dissatisfied with their current salary and vice versa. In the regression analysis, it was found that the likelihood (probability) of demotivation among teachers was more likely than among motivated teachers in the studied area. The regression coefficient between salary and demotivated teacher was significant at 10% (P<0.063)

The results of the FGD and KII also confirmed that the income of most teachers is not enough to support themselves and their families. The lack of incentives and fringe benefits, such as housing allowance and health care, made them feel dissatisfied. The person interviewed feels that his paid work cannot help him achieve the economic goals he has set for himself.

Most of the time regarding teacher salaries and benefits, I have noted that it is very important to raise the monthly salaries of teachers to a level that will allow them to meet their basic needs, and teachers should receive low-interest loans for purchase and maintenance of their own homes. This frequent question arose from teachers in schools. In the district, more than 50% of the teachers have a family home, but most of them could not get this benefit.

A left allowance for transport, health insurance, educational opportunities, and on-the-job training should be taken into account. All this is necessary to motivate the teacher to work effectively and morally.

The FGDs and KII responded that the perceived poor teacher salaries were a significant factor influencing their motivation. Growth monthly wages of teachers interviewed from ETB (5300 or USD 203.33 and (senior lead teacher) ETB 8017.

- *Interview with Chelia District Educational Office Experts.*

The final result of this research confirms the localization by Wole (2002:15) who says that income inequality between instructors and non-instructors was the maximum major source of stress (dissatisfaction) among instructors in secondary schools in Addis Ababa. This survey is also comparable to a survey conducted by Mengist, G. K. (2012) who among others found that; employees (eg, instructors) who chose the activity because of the excellent income were much more likely to have higher levels of work motivation.

Thus, the instructors had to perform additional private lessons to satisfy their monetary desires. The bad effect on their motivation is defined using the expectancy theory () which says that people are disillusioned if the effects are low in their perceived effort rating, they are told that lecturers with the donation price of life, they cannot win over the excessive load and that, that they were not able to properly complete their daily sport.

Rising rents, food prices, and transportation costs were beyond our control, and all these items were discouraging. Imagine the instructors visiting the magnificence without having breakfast. The lifestyle of instructors has a direct bad effect on their coaching motivation. Only a few of them

were able to fulfill their primary wishes by the end of each month, due to the maximum time, a few instructors should get component time paintings from distinctive non-public colleges.

When all expenses were covered, there was nothing left. To win this task, several instructors generated additional profits for his households to survive. This has major implications for the spectacular performance of the instructors in the room and the excellence of the training they provided. It also affects their commitment to educational reforms and values. This turned into an opinion expressed by means of one high school teacher: My negative income motivated my daily activities. I was actually forced to stick to various sub-activities. If I had enough money, I might want to use this time to put together lessons.

I realize that this time is being misused through my absence from class, but coaching cannot satisfy my basic desires and I want to pursue other activities in order to continue to exist. I am actually aware that more paintings influence my daily paintings (coaching).

In recent times, authorities have been constantly introducing career ladders as a method to help instructors. The addition of this career leaderboard and the associated perk is believed to have sparked heated debate. On the record, United States officers stated that a maximum number of instructors were satisfied with its introduction. However, academics within the pattern indicated that they were no longer satisfied with the way the authorities were handling the situation, and a number of academics voiced their criticism through striking means.

Moreover, these FG Ds and KIIs indicated that their salaries were disadvantageous compared to various professions. Some of the academics claimed that they did not feel as comfortable as various experts. This created dissatisfaction and overcharging for the attrition of qualified and certified instructors

Other research by Bolin (2007:59); Jyoti and Sharma (2006:355); Garrett and Ssesanga (2005:44); Maganga, M. (2016) documented that over 60% of respondents to their survey on trainers are now dissatisfied with their salaries in secondary schools in Tanzania. A nearby survey conducted by means of Wole (2002:15) additionally confirmed poor and insufficient pay and income inequalities between instructors and non-instructors as the maximum stressful (dissatisfying) element of academic work. Looking at 99.3% of trainer respondents were disillusioned with their pay (see Table 2).

The instructors felt that the salaries they received no longer matched the qualifications they had, their professions, efforts, and experience, no longer covered all their primary needs, and no longer beautified their commitment to teaching (see Table 2).

Perceived low salaries affected the values, respect, and retention of instructors in their company. It seems that the

salaries earned by academics are no longer sufficient to meet the physiological or organic needs of academics (see phase 2.1).

Additionally, their salaries are no longer commensurate with their efforts and experience, which, according to expectancy theory (Estes, B. et al., 2012), has caused coaches to be dissatisfied with their jobs.

According to Herzberg's two-element theory, if external elements such as income, fringe benefits, and support opportunities are no longer satisfying and satisfying, academics could become disillusioned with their work (see stage 2.2.).

Ethiopian training coverage indicated that action might be taken against affected instructors (MOE 1994:22). However, the effects of this view confirmed that instructors received no housing allowances in addition to their salaries. They lacked various essential benefits, despite the fact that housing and delivery offers are getting more and more expensive in line with them. Thus, academics regularly held various jobs and devoted themselves much less to teaching.

- *School Management*

The final result of the multivariate evaluation in the eleventh bench indicated that instructors who were no longer satisfied with school leadership were significantly more likely to be disengaged than influenced instructors. The common ratio of a non-influenced instructor is 25.35 times better than an influenced instructor with an inside view of areas.

As demonstrated above in Table 11, the courtship between school leadership and instructors' motivational reputation became statistically significant at 1% ($P < 0.01$, $P = 0.008$).

The director believed that if the preferred training penalty was to be achieved, trainers needed to move from the outer fringes to the very center of the training processes. They need to be involved in decision-making for their function, their work, the quality of training, curriculum development, and faculty coverage and improvement.

That is why the faculty had problem-free cooperation with the instructor in all sports, with heads of teaching, stakeholders, instructors - students, extras, and instructors' unions in solving teaching reforms.

At most, instructors expressed the opinion that they were excluded from selection within the faculty and selection with reference to promotion. Yet they were constantly predicted to introduce improvement and new initiatives. This was an interview with the Superintendent of Public High Schools in Chelia District.

During the Most Faculty Leaders Conferences, we no longer get our suggestions or talk about issues on the agenda, except for our own issues. Moreover, they autocratically determine something they need.

FGDs and KIIs shared the idea that during faculty certainty, principals are no longer equipped, supportive, or fair. In addition, they seemed to believe that the terrible exception to faculty education is associated with much less than excellent faculty management. For example, managers no longer focused on the suggestions of others.

They no longer act as advisors. Now they were oblivious to the trainer's problems; they honestly rush to write behaviour warning letters and cash from instructor salaries. This happened due to the fact that they are no longer qualified, skilled, and visionary. They became principles because of their political views. There was a professional gap between directors and instructors. They believed that they were now ill-equipped to guide and benchmark instructors on teaching issues.

Most of the faculties they were in charge of were political representatives who now no longer have the proper qualifications and are no longer dedicated to their work. For example: How is it possible to talk approximately process and faculty motivation exceptionally while instructors have no admiration for or her leaders and while training and politics are not separated while instructors and authorities see each other as enemies?

Additionally, they expressed the opinion that the surroundings of the faculty no longer allow them to expand their full potential. This is attributed to the fact that the faculties were political centres and that the heads of faculties were committed to the mission of the faculty. For example:

All the sports on the faculty campus have been associated with political issues and therefore they are disappointed.

The surrounding area of the faculty becomes the most discouraging component. It was surrounded by horrible sports, along with horrible student behaviour, horrible coach relationships, leadership bias, horrible pay, loss of professional freedom, and horrible faculty leadership.

They said back that the instructors have lost the admiration and guidance of their superiors, and they are reprimanded with the inner presence of their colleagues and students. As one example, they stated: Before the end of the school year, one instructor of legal guidelines falls seriously ill and falls into a coma. He knows the faculty above all and has to wait for the situation.

Unfortunately, they may not have helped him anymore and he passed. According to our subculture, he attended the funeral ceremony, and he became again in the faculty after wearing black clothes every week carrying black clothes primarily based exclusively on our subculture and especially the faculty.

When the professor and the supervisor noticed everyone differently and understood the case, he probably didn't even ask him about the situation anymore. He looked at him sternly and reprimanded him in the presence of his colleagues and students. His expectation became that teachers in particular could show empathy and lead, but the opposite happened.

Regarding control practices (decision-making, front-end control, exceptional control, and systems teacher), this control showed that more than half of the sample (57.8% – see Table 9) of lecturers were upset by this aspect of their work. This is constant when Weiqi (2007) decided that teachers are angry with university inspection and control systems. Also, a previous survey by VSO (2008:35) confirmed that lecturers were demotivated by way of authoritative styles of control practices in their faculties.

This difficulty does not appear to have increased over time and continues to negatively affect the job satisfaction of instructors in Ethiopian secondary faculties in Addis Ababa. Despite the many adjustments within the Ethiopian training system, along with the transformation of the current management systems, it is clear from the instructors' responses that they think that the poor first-class management they have been given will turn into demotivation.

The 1994 Ethiopian Training Newsletter declared that non-political training could be provided at any level of training.

However, the instructor has an opinion within the sample that they were exposed to political influences because of the ideologies of their faculty heads. This confirms previous opinions. For example, the training neighbourhood improvement software indicated the need for development in faculty leadership (Saiti, A. (2012). The report stated that inappropriate and uncoordinated school publications with the help of faculty leaders were now unable to overcome high school management situations and that it remained poor. This investigation shows that poor control had a bad impact on the enjoyment of the instructors' activities.

✓ *Secondary School Management Systems*

An alternative component that noticeably affects the reputation of teachers' motivation has become Teachers Management gadgets. As shown in Table 14, it negatively affects the reputation of coach motivation at a 5% level of significance ($P < 0.05$, considering value=0.046).

The logit version predicts that the useless Teacher Management gadget demotivates the coach, not inspires them. The odds ratio of becoming an uninspired trainer was 0.046 times better than an inspired trainer due to the unusable trainer control device

According to the interview with Gedo Main Secondary School, the majority of lecturers interviewed were no longer satisfied with the maximum practices of managerial and administrative assistance (see Table 4).

Administrative assistance and management practices that were viewed and perceived negatively and as highly unsatisfactory include the following, specifically the terrible administrative assistance of schools, primarily the reduced dedication of instructors; lack of supply of educational materials; ineffective administrative assistance with regard to pupils' disciplinary problems; unfair decisions and assessment of lecturers' images by school management; terrible college policies; a terrible, undemocratic and transformative mainstream management style; the loss of the ability of university principals to discover the strengths of lecturers; the loss of appreciation of tutors through scholars and mother and father and the loss of tutors' reputation for well-finished paintings.

• *Working Environment*

The result of the multivariate analysis in Table 23 showed that there is a significant relationship between the work environment and the teacher's motivational state. Finally, some teachers expressed their dissatisfaction with the lack of teaching-learning resources and facilities in schools.

This study found that many secondary school teachers spoke positively about their profession and the value of their profession to children's development. The teachers in the study by Perrachione et al. (2008:8) stated that working with students was one of the reasons for their satisfaction with teaching.

However, it is interesting to note that a significant number of teachers were nevertheless satisfied with their teaching duties. The teacher clearly expressed his concern for his students and his belief that their teaching develops the children. When teachers perceived their workload as unfair, their job dissatisfaction increased. Although a significant number of teachers were dissatisfied with the demand for their jobs, they were satisfied with the workload within their department, with the working hours and the time they had for socializing (see Table 5).

This study revealed that teachers had satisfactory relationships with colleagues in their departments and this sense of collegiality implied shared responsibility and thereby created satisfaction.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ Conclusion

The effectiveness and efficiency of competition in the labor market results from the motivation factors of human resources, work competences among employees, which depend on skills and knowledge.

A higher proportion of teacher respondents were demotivated compared to motivated teachers in the study areas.

When it comes to teachers' opinions about their job satisfaction, a higher percentage of respondents were dissatisfied with the time they had for leadership and work as such.

Regarding gender, sampled male teachers were more demotivated than sampled female teachers.

This confirms that male teachers were significantly demotivated compared to female teachers in the researched area.

However, eight variables (gender, age, and education level, current marginal benefit of encouragement, administrative support, workload, job satisfaction, and sufficient available learning materials) were found to be statistically insignificant.

➤ Recommendations and Policy Implications

- The education sector should improve the working environment and working conditions in secondary school. This should be done in order to motivate teachers to work.
- The school authority and other concerned authorities should work on a system that can increase teachers' interest in their profession.
- Education authority and other concerned authorities should work on teacher benefits and fringe benefits
- The school authority and other concerned authorities should work on the disciplinary problems of the students.

- The school board should operate under conditions that cause employee job dissatisfaction (teaching profession, insufficient pay and other benefits, work environment, student disciplinary problems, administrative problems) and poor performance by facilitating teacher advancement through salary increases and other benefits.

➤ Recommendations for Further Research

This study provides information on factors influencing teacher motivation of secondary school teachers in Chelia Woreda and is recommended to be replicated in other parts of the country. Future research should include the views and understandings of school principals, educational leaders, and principals and examine how interpersonal relationships between teachers, parents, and principals can be improved.

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